

Research Article

Cloud Security: The Use and Significance in Information Security Management

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Abstract: Cloud security is another term for security in cloud computing. It is a set of policies, controls, procedures, and technologies that come together to develop cloud security to secure the infrastructure, data and cloud-based systems. These security procedures are set up for protecting cloud data, assisting regulatory compliance, protecting consumer privacy, and establishing authentication policies for certain users and devices. Computer, IT, and information security are all closely related to cloud security. Each individual and organisation requires IT infrastructure on a regular basis, therefore security is an important aspect in this context. Cloud security is an important key term in the computing field, and it is becoming more common in many organisations and institutions. In this paper the use and significance influence of cloud security has been described. There are explanations on how cloud security works and reasons why cloud security is an important aspect in information security management. This paper is purposely to identify how far this cloud security is influencing information security.

Keywords: cloud security; information technology (IT); significance

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1. INTRODUCTION

The cloud provides an accessible way for storing and accessing data from anywhere by using an internet connection. Users may easily save their local data on a distant server with a cloud application. The term "cloud computing" also refers to the technology that supports the cloud, which typically consists of some type of virtualized IT infrastructure, such as servers, operating systems, networking, and other infrastructure that has been abstracted using specialised software to enable pooling and dividing across physical hardware boundaries. Virtualization enables cloud providers to maximise the use of their data centre resources. Not surprisingly, many organisations are starting to depend on cloud services. For the data of their users to remain private and secure, cloud providers must abide by security and privacy policies. Cloud security is another term for security in cloud computing. Cloud security is one type of cybersecurity. It is a collection of technology, protocols, and best practises that secure cloud computing environments, applications operating in the cloud, and data kept in the cloud. Cloud security works to offer access control, data governance and compliance, disaster recovery, and storage and network protection against internal and external threats. Securing cloud services starts by understanding exactly what is being protected and the system aspects that must be managed. Cloud security guards against theft, leakage, and deletion of data stored online via cloud computing platforms. Firewalls, penetration

testing, obfuscation, tokenization, virtual private networks (VPN), and avoiding public internet connections are some techniques for providing cloud security. Controls and process enhancements for cloud security include those that strengthen the system, alert prospective attackers, and track down problems when they do happen. A business continuity plan and data backup strategy should be considered when thinking about cloud security in the event of a security breach or other emergency. For the hybrid cloud, private cloud, and public cloud, there are several cloud security solutions using a variety of methods. In public cloud settings, the security of hardware and software is the responsibility of the cloud provider, and the user is in charge of protecting their own assets, such as virtual machines, apps, and data.

2. DISCUSSION

2.1 *The Use of Cloud Security*

Most organisations use cloud security as their security tools for the organisation's data, as cloud security is a set of practices and tools created to handle both internal and external security risks to organisations. Organisations need cloud security to implement their modernization plans and integrate cloud-based tools and services into their infrastructure. So, this shows that cloud security has several uses that make it so important for organisations. There are several reasons why most organisations or companies use cloud security as their security tool.

The first is that organisations use cloud security as their guard for their servers. It is because the ordinary and basic network did not properly provide any type of protection to guarantee the servers' complete security, so the threats have to be avoided by the servers themselves. So, by using cloud security, a bunch of data is sent to the cloud rather than going straight to the servers. Only authorised users are granted access once the cloud analyses the data. The cloud also prevents an unapproved bunch of data from reaching the server. Apart from that, cloud security is also a technological element that prevents threats from happening on the server. The accessibility and exposure of sensitive data can be restricted by clients and providers using the tools and technology of cloud security. To make this happen, encryption is the most suitable technique or method of cloud security to prevent threats from occurring. The client's data is encrypted to prevent unauthorised parties from decrypting it. It will be impossible to access and useless if the client's data disappears or is taken.

The second is that organisations use cloud security to manage data and secure encryption. It is because complex algorithms are used in encryption techniques to hide and secure data. These techniques allow the identification of data that is managed via cloud security, which also restricts access from unknown software that may decrypt the encrypted files. Apart from that, the organisation may encrypt its data both at rest and in transit to further protect it while it is stored in the cloud. Without the organisation's confidential decryption key, it is very difficult for anybody to view the data.

The third one is that the organisation uses cloud security to examine and sort data. It is because the applications in conventional systems analyse the data before it gets to the server, plus the applications are expensive and difficult to keep up with. After it enters the application network, it filters the data that arrives. The devices in the organisation occasionally experience overload and may shut down, obstructing both good and bad data and possibly failing to perform as planned. But, by using cloud web security services, a bunch of data is diverted to the security cloud first, where it is screened before being forwarded to the application system. With this, the data in the organisation will be secured, and sort of like cloud security, it will be filtered first to make sure no bad data or information can enter the systems.

The fourth one is that the organisation uses cloud security because it has a private cloud option. The private cloud option means any cloud service created specifically for use by only one organisation. The organisation will not share its cloud computing resources with any other organisation. Private clouds can be tailored to a company's specific business and security requirements. Organisations may now manage compliance-sensitive IT operations without sacrificing the security and performance that used to

be only possible with specialised data centres on premises, thanks to increased visibility and control over the infrastructure. In addition, the private cloud option assures security against issues with shared resources.

The last one is that the organisation uses cloud security because it provides legal compliance for organisations. It is because clients and organisations privacy must be protected in order to be in accordance with the law. In order to protect the database's security, cloud-based security has established compliance guidelines that must be properly adhered to. Apart from that, it is also the law and regulations that were set by the government. It is because governments are now aware of how crucial it is to prevent the commercial exploitation of private information. Therefore, organisations must obey the regulations in order to maintain their policies. Plus, laws and regulations require the organisations to uphold strict privacy and client data protection requirements so that the client's data and the organisation's data itself will be protected. In addition, these are some of the uses of cloud security that benefit the users, which are organisations or companies, in order for them to keep their data safe from any harm or threats.

2.2. Key of Cloud Security Use Case

Use cases are a way of locating, outlining, and organising system needs in system evaluation. The use case consists of a number of potential interactions between people and systems in a certain environment that are connected to a specific objective. The procedure generates a document that lists each step a user took to finish a particular task. Cloud security also has its own use cases. Besides, there are also some excellent potentials for cloud security services, which sometimes depend on the distinctive characteristics of the cloud environment itself. There are a few key use cases for cloud security that will be discussed.

The first one is privileged account access. Account management is one of the most important security controls in a cloud environment. It is because accounts must be set up with the "least privileges" necessary for them to carry out their tasks, and their usage must always be watched. Apart from that, for administrator accounts on cloud platforms, this is especially crucial. It would be simple for an intruder to modify firewall configurations or add services where necessary if an account like this were compromised. So, to impose responsibility, general accounts like admin, administrator, or root should not be utilised. It's important to keep an eye on unusual behaviour and compare it to planned adjustments. Plus, any access from places outside of where an organisation anticipates conducting its operations should be noted and looked into. This will give the user a privileged account to access their own account without any problems, such as hackers' problems hacking accounts, and to keep the information private.

The second one is data exfiltration. Data exfiltration is the act of an authorised individual removing information from secured systems where it belongs and either sharing it with uninvited people or transferring it to unsecure systems. The majority of the time, a cloud environment has a wealth of useful data for an intruder. So, organisations move systems into the cloud due to the importance of the data as well as the requirement for highly accessible and available platforms. This will prevent data exfiltration from happening as the organisation moves important and useful data to the cloud security system. Although there may not be much data in the cloud environment itself, the technology may be used to smuggle local data out of the on-premises network, perhaps getting around firewall restrictions and traffic alarms. Any suspicious data leaving the cloud systems that may be huge in bulk, apply a questionable network port, or include certain strings or headers needs to be at least monitored and additionally prevented depending on the confidence of the detections. In addition, organisations must incorporate security knowledge and best practices into their culture in order to lower the likelihood of data exfiltration. Every contact with computer networks, devices, applications, data, and other users must be continually risk-evaluated.

The third one is a man-in-the-cloud attack. It is a hacker who has the ability to access users' entire drives, including all of the papers stored there, and steal data. So, this use case focuses on an authentication token that can be found on a computer or mobile device. A local application can apply this token to use automated user authentication on cloud platforms. By replacing that token with a different one, a hacker hopes to divert the user and their data to their own cloud account. The outcome can be a direct synchronisation of the victim's data with the hacker's system. This behaviour might be found and often stopped by keeping track of connections to unfamiliar cloud instances through endpoint monitoring, network SSL decryption, or a Cloud Access Security Broker (CASB).

The last one is threat intelligence analysis. Threat intelligence data offers insight on attacker origins, compromise indications, and behavioural trends connected to assaults against various types of cloud services, as well as usage patterns for cloud accounts. Learning machine engines in the cloud may be used to collect and evaluate threat intelligence inputs on a large scale. Additionally, data for probability or prediction models can be handled. This cloud security use case could be an ideal addition to a cloud security system given the rise in cloud assaults, including account hijacking attempts. Microsoft's Advanced Threat Analytics is one example of threat intelligence analysis software.

2.3 The Significance of Cloud Computing

The main significance of cloud computing is the strategic development of services. Strategic development, in its simplest terms, refers to how the organisation generates revenue from current core plans and core resources by optimising or reimagining how the service or product is offered. Cloud services make it possible to access the most recent software without the need for extra installation resources, giving traders a strategic edge. The rapid installation of the latest software enables businesses to increase their computer capacity while avoiding large capital investments and expensive programming expenses. Next, the second significance of working with cloud computing is its excellent service controllability. According to the cloud service level agreement (SLA), cloud service solutions include services such as security, problem-solving, management of the infrastructure, and maintenance. These services may be designed to meet specific business requirements that can eliminate the need for businesses to purchase expensive servers and allow companies to manage their own information technology (IT) systems.

Next, cloud-based computing is chosen due to its low cost. Cloud computing is less expensive than physical infrastructure. It may replace hardware like hard drives, network switches, servers, and generators with just one system that is simple to analyse and manage. With all this, it makes cloud services more cost-effective in the long term. Furthermore, cloud computing has a tiering or tiered system, which means that there is less overhead and organisations simply pay for the capabilities and space they demand.

One of the most significant advantages of cloud computing is collaboration. The cloud service is widely used because of its electronic data interchange. Data interchange using cloud-based computing requires less time than physical services, and it allows several people to update and execute the exact same file at the same time. Many cloud services also have social capabilities that enable teams to interact, share, and use data in the cloud more efficiently. Following that, cloud computing is significant due to its unpredictability in batch processing. Continuous development and growth involve the management of massive volumes of data by an organisation. Cloud services allow for the quick batch processing of massive amounts of data without the need for human interaction, which boosts the quality of the data and business productivity.

Another significance of using cloud computing is the simplicity with which it may be implemented. Businesses may simply move to and adapt to the use of cloud services. This kind of action allows businesses to keep their applications without the need for extra technological capabilities, making

the shift to the cloud faster and easier. Additionally, cloud computing eliminates the need for hardware. Servers, physically or electronically, need the acquisition and upkeep of expensive hardware and software. However, cloud computing, on the other hand, requires no hardware and eliminates the requirement for data in physical storage. Companies may thus develop a cloud system that matches their demands and simply extend it if necessary.

Cloud-based computing is also quite accessible. Organisational downtime can result in financial losses, company disruption, loss of revenue, and negative reputational consequences. As a result, it matters a lot for businesses to have minimal or no downtime. Because of its decentralised operations, the cloud service enables outstanding usability for organisations, which is one of its most significant advantages. Ultimately, cloud computing gives employees security of employment. Reliability is essential for the smooth functioning of companies of all sizes. The cloud service prevents security breaches, outages, and disruptions. The service also maintains, updates, and upgrades these services on a regular basis. Furthermore, the cloud successfully manages failure scenarios and guarantees that recovery operations are automated.

3. CONCLUSION

Cloud computing security is a new technology development that has the potential to have a great influence on information security management. It has many uses and has a significant influence on its users. To ensure the security of the assets hosted in the cloud, select the finest cloud security service. Cloud security is the precaution taken to safeguard digital assets and data kept online via cloud services. Additionally, it is obvious that cloud security is ideal for information security management given its widespread use and significant influence.

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